

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B089
Date: 05 Apr 2005
Take Off: 10:41:59
Landing: 15:21:01
Flight Time: 4h39m02

Campaign: CIRRUS FLIGHT 1

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Bristol Channel (Area A) in layers of cirrus cloud likely to be anthropogenically influenced

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist	Richard Cotton	Met Office
4	ADA/CPI / Mission Scientist (training)	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Detachment Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	PTrMS	Dave Oram	UEA
10	NOxy	David Stewart	UEA
11	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
12	WAS Training	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
13	PAN / WAS	Jim Hopkins	York University
14	Cloud Physics & CCM2 (training)	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
15	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B089
 Date: 5/4/2005
 Project: Cirrus
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
073027		Start posn	0.00 kft	077	52'12.56N, 0'10.45E
101551		inu to navigate	-.24 kft	078	
101943		Engines 1+4 start	-.24 kft	078	
102310		power change	-.24 kft	078	to a/c power
102652		taxy/tow start	-.23 kft	078	tow due to airfield work
103158		power change back	-.24 kft	213	to gnd power
103420		engine 2+3 start	-.24 kft	213	
103610		power change	-.24 kft	213	to a/c power
103747		Aircraft Taxy	-.24 kft	213	
104050		Engines Up	-.24 kft	229	waiting for t/o run
104159		t/o	-.26 kft	230	from cambridge
105000		asp open	11.0 kft	244	
111221	114719	profile 1	11.0 - 18.0 kft	244	
112011		profile 1	18.0 kft		interrupted
113135		Profile 1	18.0 - 31.0 kft	253	resumed
120129	121129	Run 1	18.0 kft	075	Brief Item C
121333	122034	Profile 2	18.0 - 12.0 kft	242	
122127	122407	Profile 3	12.0 - 10.0 kft	244	
122602	123603	Run 2	11.0 kft	246	Brief Item C
123933	124934	Run 3	12.0 kft	070	Brief Item D
125118	130120	Run 4	13.0 kft	266	Brief Item D
130329	131426	Run 5	14.0 kft	075	Brief Item D
131711	132709	Run 6	18.0 kft	258	Brief Item E
133201	134222	Run 7	24.0 kft	079	Brief item E
134506	140308	Profile 4	24.0 - 35.1 kft	256	
135110		Profile 4	29.6 kft	256	reduced rate of climb to 700ft/min
140727	141728	Run 8	35.0 kft	086	Brief Item F
141955	142956	Run 9	33.0 - 33.1 kft	261	
143319	144320	Run 10	31.1 - 31.0 kft	077	
151303		asp closed	10.0 kft	106	
152101		land	-.22 kft	230	at cambridge
152535		chocks, before tow	-.21 kft	064	
152834		ground power	-.21 kft	064	
152852		engine overspeeds	-.21 kft	064	engine shutdown
152951		final position	-.21 kft	064	52'12.58, 0'10.86

B089 Track 05-APR-05

Sortie Title UTLS Cirrus- Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1

Scientific Aims:

1. To measure the total number of Condensation Nuclei (CN), CCN, IN and the size distribution of optically active particles in clean and polluted air in the UTLS region over the UK. Assessment of their spatial distribution and their likely source based on tracer measurements and air mass history.
2. To quantify the extent to which air mass history, and gas and particle loading can affect the microphysical properties of cirrus clouds in the UTLS region, in particular, the size distribution, phase and morphology of cloud particles.
3. To obtain estimates of HNO₃ loss to cirrus clouds and the subsequent effect on the aerosol population after the cloud has evaporated using case studies involving one or more wave clouds.
4. To make observations of the number, size distribution, phase and morphology of droplets and crystals in cirrus cloud and the number and size distribution of interstitial particles and correlate these with measurements of tracers that identify anthropogenic influence. Hence building on objective 3 to investigate the influence of cirrus on the distribution of aerosol and gases in the UTLS region as cloud and precipitation evaporate.
5. To make an assessment of the chemical composition of the particulate in the UTLS region as a function of their size, their spatial variability and the effect different sources have on their composition.
6. To use measurements of the masses of key components as a function of size of cirrus particle dry residues and interstitial particles to determine if there are distinct chemical differences between activated and unactivated particles.
7. To establish the partitioning of oxidised nitrogen between the gas and aerosol phases as a function of air mass history and source region

Weather conditions

Cirrus cloud preferably associated with the polar front jet preferably over the UK.

Key Measurements

All instruments to be operated continuously.

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 (and SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- Ice Nucleus counter (INC) normally operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.

- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.
- FWVS – Switch off the lamp when frost point rises above -15C. Calibration should be performed following altitude changes.
- WAS - One bottle sample per flight leg.
- AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet.

Sortie Brief UTLS Cirrus- Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1

Flight Number B089

Date 05 April 2005

Sortie Aims: To make measurements of the microphysics of cirrus clouds and their interaction with local aerosol and oxides of nitrogen. To investigate the effects of precipitation from the cloud on the vertical distribution of aerosol and oxidized nitrogen

Sortie Location: In layers of cirrus cloud likely to be anthropogenically influenced.

Sortie Summary: The aircraft will initially make a vertical profile from well below cloud base to above the top of the cirrus. It will then make a series of straight and level runs of 10 minutes duration at several altitudes below, in and, when possible, above the cloud top. The straight and level runs above and below cloud will concentrate on determining the gaseous composition and aerosol physical and chemical properties of the air. Measurements of the vertical wind velocity will be made here. A straight and level run will be made very close to cloud base to determine whether supercooled water droplets or ice crystals are being activated.. Runs progressively deeper into the cloud will then be flown. SLRs will also be made in the fall streaks of the cirrus to characterise the precipitation in this region and to investigate the influence of the evaporation of the precipitation on the aerosol properties and trace gases in the region of the fall streaks.

Sortie Detail

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL200 for transit to operating area.
- b. T+40 Perform vertical profile through cirrus from below cloud base to aircraft ceiling, or to above cirrus top whichever is the lower.
- c. T+60 Descend to below cirrus perform straight and level run along the mean wind speed 300 feet below cloud base for 10 minutes.
- d. T+75 Turn through 180 degrees Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run for 10 minutes just in cloud at the base of the generating cells just in cloud. Deviations from the straight run may be made to penetrate generating cells.
- e. T+90 Turn through 180 degrees ascend to middle of cloud and perform straight and level run for 10 minutes
- f. T+105 Turn through 180 degrees and if possible ascend to above cloud top and perform straight and level run duration 10 minutes above cloud top
- g. T+120 Descend to below cirrus base and make level runs through fall streaks adjusting flight path to pass through fall streaks as required.
- h. T+135 Descend to lowest altitude reached by fall streaks and make and level runs through the residue.
- i. Repeat items b to h as time permits
- j. T+290 return transit
- k. T+330 Land

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No A 8087

Date 5/4/05

Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				VERY DIFFUSE MID-LEVEL CLOUDS
				DIFFICULT TO SEE CLOUD BASE / TOP.
		FL310		CONTINUES
				CANNOT REACH $\frac{1}{2}$ ABOVE
				WORK IN CLOUD LAYER THAT
				PROFILED THROUGH.
117714	P1	END		
		FL256		(P1) ICE (RY) STARS
		FL240		IN CLOUD BUT DIFFUSE.
				CLOUD BASE
115817		FL190		Tc = -23°C Td = -20°C W 270°
				VERY DIFFUSE.
		FL180		CAN SEE SEA BELOW.
P1 START		FL180		WILL DO FIRST RUN AT FL180
120129				IN CLOUD, ICE DROPS.
				DESCEND TO FL140 TO TRY
P1 END	121130	FL180		AND GET BETTER IDEA OF CLOUD BASE.
P 121323	P2 START		WEST-DIRECTION.	
				NO CLEAR CLOUD BASE
	P3 START			KEEP DESCENDING
	TURBULENCE		FL 116	

Aircraft Scientist's Log

15:45

Flight No A/B089

Date 5/4/05

Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				TURBULENCE - T ₀ /T _C INDICATE CLOUD BASE
	R1 END	FL100		cloud base 115
12:26:05	R2 START	FL110		will do run at 110.
12:26:25		ITEM C(ii)		TURBULENCE
12:30:03	R2 END			CAN SEE SEA BELOW CLOUD-BASE IS VAGUE/INDISTINCT SO MAYBE DO TWO ITEM DS? AT FL120 AND FL130
12:39:40	R3 START	ITEM D(i) 50.5N 6.6W		IN CLOUD - NEAR BASE FL 120
		FL120		3/8 SE BELOW ICE HALO
				T _C = -12.2 T _{DEL} = -15.6
				WIND = 263 22ms
12:40:04				TURBULENCE
12:49:30	R3 END	FL120		T _C = -13.0 T _D = -12.5°C
			50.8N 5.4W	
(R3) 12:51:19	R4 START	FL130	D(ii)	T _C = -15.4 T _D = -11.6 WIND 23ms 271°
	(R2)			
13:01:29	R4 END	FL130		
13:03:24	R5 START	FL140	D(iii)	LESS TURBULENCE ADD 300 RUN NEAR BASE DECA-SE INDISTINCT.
13:14:27	R5 END			T _C = -16.1°C T _D = -13.3°C IN CLOUD.
13:17:08	R6 START	FL180	E(i)	T _C = -21.1 T _D = -18.6
13:27:06	R6 END	FL180		BULLET REJECTED (R)
13:32:01	R7 START	FL240	E(ii)	T _C = -34.5°C T _D = -31.4°C
	R7 END	"		

300 F

-240 E2

780 E1

140 D3

30 D2

20 D1

110 (R2)

FL100 G1

FL90 G2

2 AN

Forecast T_{APH1} (T₁₃₆) ~ 700mb (FL120) -4°C 1000

T_C = -56°C at FL310, so can climb to FL350.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No ~~A~~ B087

Date 5/4/05

Page 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				ASCEND TO GET ABOVE CLOUD
134514	P4	FL240		INDISTINCT CLOUD TOP
		FL340		1/8 CI ABOVE, CLEARLY ABOVE CLOUD THAT MEASURED EARLIER
		FL350		SEEK. 100% RAILS 90-3N2 5.2 FF/FU
140301	P4 END	FL350		T _D = -54.5°C T _C = -59.4°C
				1/8 CI ABOVE
140727	R8	OPTIM (F)	FL350	ABOUT CLOUD
140705				60 UNDER 1/8 CI - DEFINITELY OLD CONTRAIL - S
141730	R8 END			(PERSISTANT CONTRAILS WITH FALL STREAKS)
141957	R9 START		FL330	TAY AND GO THROUGH HIGHER LEVEL CLOUD
142954	R9 END			T _C = -54.6°C T _D = -50.9°C
				1/8 CI ABOVE.
				4.4 FF/FU N2S7 PERSISTANT CONTRAIL - JUST ABOVE
				CP1 BULLET PROJECTIONS *
143320	R10 ST.	SI. IN	FL310	FL310 TAY
		5.5W.		T _C = -50.9°C T _D = -46°C
				WIND 28ms ⁻¹ 259°
				IN PATCHY CLOUDS, INDISTINCT LAYERING.
144320	R10 END		FL310	
		TRANSIT	BACK.	

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Yes
All cylinders pressures are OK	Yes
Ozone Span = 514, Offset = 50	

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	42	140	128
POST FLIGHT	31	140	150

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.5	0.5	1.111	0.071	0.485
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
	33.46	1.13	7.27	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	09:03 0	1	-1	0	0	-1	-0.167
NO (ppbV)	08:50 0.30	0.31	0.33	0.30	0.25	0.20	0.28
NO₂ (ppbV)	08:51 0.75	0.80	0.94	1.07	1.11	0.99	0.94
NO_x (ppbV)	08:52 1.14	1.10	1.22	1.31	1.40	1.42	1.265
SO₂ (ppbV)	08:58 -0.61	-1.11	-1.33	-1.20	-1.34	-0.74	-1.055

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

1st cal was bad @ 10:18 so cancelled and restarted.
 Before take off there were three power changeovers due to only being able to start two engines, being towed, then starting the remaining two engines after ground power was inserted. Thus lamp cooled a little more than it normally would.
 Initial flows were a little low (19-34 and 6.9 – 7.2) until the gentle instrument side thump fix was applied.
 After this the taxi cal had to be abandoned as it would not complete before take off.

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	1 Apr 2005 : 13:07:14	82.63	84.46	6979.80

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
5 Apr 2005 10:22:04	Ground pre-taxi (580-599)	64.13	114.93	7370.67	42.44	6.25	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		29.65					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
10:53:54	FL100 (513-502)	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		62.87	115.78	7278.92	49.13	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.84	0.7	0.8	1.085	0.069	0.344
Time	Flight Level	CO					
11:12:33	FL110 (513-506)	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		62.10	116.15	7213.23	49.47	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.91	0.7	0.8	1.084	0.066	0.341
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
11:4?	FL310	Air vent cap on					
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
12:00	FL180	Air vent cap off					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:04:01	FL180	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		57.03	122.29	6973.52	50.00	7.01	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.33	0.7	0.8	1.044	0.067	0.262
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:29:22	FL110	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		59.31	119.18	7068.59	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.90	0.7	0.8	1.068	0.068	0.346
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:42:49	FL120	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		58.65	120.36	7058.76	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.87					

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:54:55	FL130	58.09	121.24	7042.62	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.88	0.7	0.8	1.061	0.066	0.322
Time	Flight Level	CO					
13:08:21	FL140	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		57.79	122.05	7053.69	50.00	7.12	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.90	0.7	0.8	1.057	0.066	0.309
Time	Flight Level	CO					
13:22:46	FL180 CAL WAS BAD	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		57.71	121.51	7012.34	50.00	7.07	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.62					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
13:35:50	FL240	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		55.27	124.99	6908.71	50.00	7.07	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.58	0.7	0.8	1.007	0.066	0.190
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
13:56	FL310	Air vent cap on					
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
14:06	FL350	SO2 flow pressure low. Pressure: 182.6; Flow 0.00					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
14:10:46	FL350	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		45.79	58.32	7250.00	50.00	6.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.85	0.7	0.8	0.921	0.064	0.0
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
14:35	FL315	Increased as descent reached FL315					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
14:36:37	FL310	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		47.47	147.34	6991.48	50.00	6.67	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.85	0.7	0.8	0.973	0.065	0.107

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

SO2 Instrument readings

Time	SO ₂
12:39:40 (R3)	-0.26
12:39:50	-0.61
12:40:00	-0.32
12:40:10	-0.17
12:40:20	-0.41
12:40:30	0.01
12:40:40	0.02
12:40:50	-0.38
12:41:00	-0.50
12:41:10	-0.67
12:41:20	0.00
12:41:30	-0.43
12:41:40	-0.86
12:41:50	-0.85
12:42:00	-0.18
12:42:10	-0.36
12:42:20	-0.50
12:42:30	-0.18
12:42:40	0.05
12:42:50	-0.52
12:43:00	-0.63

Time	SO ₂
12:43:10	-0.72
12:43:20	-0.18
12:43:30	-1.45
12:43:40	-0.50
12:43:50	-0.57
12:44:00	-0.00
12:44:10	-0.58
12:44:20	-0.23
12:44:30	-0.32
12:44:40	-
12:44:50	-0.58
12:45:00	-0.25
12:45:10	-0.42
12:45:20	-0.97
12:45:30	-
12:45:40	-0.45
12:45:50	-0.33
12:46:00	-0.78
12:46:10	-0.67
12:46:20	-0.76
12:46:30	-0.65

Time	SO ₂
12:46:40	-0.68
12:46:50	-0.87
12:47:00	0.06
12:47:10	-0.61
12:47:20	-0.69
12:47:30	-0.44
12:47:40	-0.54
12:47:50	-0.92
12:48:00	0.51
12:48:10	-0.34
12:48:20	-0.53
12:48:30	-1.11
12:48:40	-0.76
12:48:50	-0.21
12:49:00	-0.51
12:49:10	-0.76
12:49:20	-0.39
12:49:30	-0.54
12:49:40	-0.36
End of R3	

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B089

Date: 5/04/05

Operator: MAP

Page 1 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:12:28	Lower		15	Computer U/S	15	800	8	1700	800	11	Start Profile 1 from FL110
11:13:33	Channels				10	600	8	2000	800	11	FL120
11:14:40	Missing				10	800	8	2200	800	11	FL130
11:15:38					30	800	8	5300	800	11	FL140
11:16:55			16		20	800	8	3400	1000	8	FL150
11:18:00					25	500	4	3000	400	11	FL160
11:19:04			17		100	375	10	9000	600	4	FL170
11:20:08					20	800	4	4000	450	4	FL180
11:32:50			19		4	500	10	900	400	11	FL190
11:33:39					12	400	10	900	200	11	FL200
11:34:44					15	250	10	1200	200	11	FL210
11:35:43					10	200	10	2000	200	11	FL220
11:36:43					20	150	10	1000	200	11	FL230
11:37:40					11	150	10	500	200	11	FL240
11:38:35					5	225	10	800	200	11	FL250
11:39:42			20		20	200	10	133	200	11	FL260
11:40:55					10	200	10	90	200	11	FL270
11:42:00					10	200	10	90	200	11	FL280
11:43:26					5	150	10	Noise			FL290
11:45:18					7	150	10	Noise			FL300
11:47:22								Noise			End of Profile 1 @ FL310
12:01:50								Noise			Start Run 1 @ FL180
12:02:00			21		20	800	9	Noise			
12:04:00					5	600	4	2500	400	11	
12:06:00			22		5	500	4	3100	400	11	
12:08:00					1	500	10	800	400	11	
12:10:00					5	400	10	2000	200	11	
12:11:40											End of Run 1
12:13:35					7	400	10	300	200	11	Start Profile 2 from FL180
12:14:50					2	350	10	2500	200	11	FL170
12:15:43					2	500	10	1000	200	11	FL160
12:16:39					4	550	10	960	400	11	FL150

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B089

Date: 5/04/05

Operator: MAP

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:17:40			22		12	600	8	1600	400	11	FL140
12:19:08					5	600	4	1500	400	11	FL130
12:20:41					5	800	7	940	600	11	End of Profile 2 @ FL120
12:21:35					10	800	7	100	800	11	Start Profile 3 from FL120
12:22:46					11	600	8	1900	800	11	
12:24:10			23								End of Profile 3 @ FL100
12:26:02											Start Run 2 @ FL110
12:27:00					12	800	4	1300	800	11	
12:29:00					5	800	8	1350	800	11	
12:31:00					5	400	10	130	200	11	
12:33:00			24								
12:35:00											
12:36:08											End of Run 2
12:39:33											Start Run 3 @ FL120
12:40:00											
12:42:00											
12:44:00					3	400	10	1200	200	11	
12:46:00					10	400	10	1000	400	11	
12:48:00					10	600	10	1600	400	11	
12:49:39											End of Run 3
12:51:20											Start Run 4 @ FL130
12:52:00					2	800	8	400	600	11	
12:54:00					10	800	8	1400	600	11	
12:56:00			25		7	600	8	1900	600	11	
12:58:00					10	700	4	2200	800	11	
13:00:00					10	800	8	2100	600	11	
13:01:35											End of Run 4
13:03:30											Start Run 5 @ FL140
13:04:00					10	600	8	1600	600	11	
13:06:00			26		6	800	8	900	600	11	
13:08:00					12	700	8	1200	600	11	
13:10:00			27		15	800	8	2300	600	11	

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B089

Date: 5/04/05

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:12:00			27		15	675	4	2000	600	11	
13:14:26											End of Run 5
13:17:12											Start Run 6 @ FL180
13:18:00			28		5	550	8	675	600	11	
13:20:00					20	500	10	250	200	11	
13:22:00			28		5	450	10	1000	200	11	
13:24:00					10	550	10	2600	200	11	
13:26:00					2	500	4	800	400	11	
13:27:11											End of Run 6
13:32:02											Start Run 7 @ FL240
13:33:00			29		5	350	10	900	200	11	
13:35:00					10	375	10	500	200	11	
13:37:00			30					200	200	11	
13:39:00					2	300	10	450	200	11	
13:41:00					5	275	10	1000	200	11	
13:42:22											End of Run 7
13:45:10											Start Profile 4 from FL240
13:46:14					2	350	10	Noise			FL250
13:47:12					6	250	10	Noise			FL260
13:48:29					4	175	10	Noise			FL270
13:49:15					1	125	10	Noise			FL280
13:50:22					1	100	11	Noise			FL290
13:51:50					2	100	11	Noise			FL300
13:53:22					15	100	11	Noise			FL310
13:55:00											FL320
13:56:52					2	50	11	Noise			FL330
13:59:07											FL340
14:03:08					6	125	10	Noise			End of Profile 4 @ FL350
14:07:29											Start Run 8 @ FL350
14:08:00								Noise			
14:10:00					2	200	10	Noise			
14:12:00					2	200	10	Noise			

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B089
Date: 05/04/2005

Campaign Name: CIRRUS
Operator: J. Hopkins
(York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (aprx.)(bar)
10:56:39	10:57:39	1	1st level run (NOxy cals)	0.98
12:06:01	12:07:01	2	FL180 just below cloud base	0.56
12:28:31	12:29:31	3	FL110 just below cloud base (c on sortie brief)	0.97
12:32:00	12:33:00	4	FL110 just below cloud base (c on sortie brief)	0.97
12:42:01	12:43:01	5	FL120 at cloud base (d on sortie brief)	0.90
12:46:00	12:47:00	6	FL120 at cloud base (d on sortie brief)	0.90
12:53:59	12:54:59	7	FL130 at cloud base ? (d2- addition to sortie brief)	0.84
12:57:30	12:58:30	8	FL130 at cloud base ? (d2- addition to sortie brief)	0.84
13:06:30	13:07:30	9	FL140 at cloud base ? (d3- addition to sortie brief)	0.78
13:09:41	13:10:41	10	FL140 at cloud base ? (d3- addition to sortie brief)	0.78
13:20:00	13:21:00	11	FL180 middle of cloud (e on sortie brief)	
13:23:00	13:24:00	12	FL180 middle of cloud (e on sortie brief)	0.56
13:35:10	13:36:10	13	FL240 middle of cloud ? (e2- addition to sortie brief)	0.29
13:38:31	13:39:31	14	FL240 middle of cloud ? (e2- addition to sortie brief)	0.29
14:10:10	14:11:10	15	FL350 above cloud (f on sortie brief)	-0.08
14:14:31	14:15:31	16	FL350 above cloud (f on sortie brief)	-0.08
14:23:01	14:24:01	17	FL330 above cloud ? (f2 addition to sortie)	-0.03
14:25:59	14:26:59	18	FL330 above cloud ? (f2 addition to sortie)	-0.03
14:36:00	14:37:00	19	FL310	0.03
14:40:00	14:41:00	20	FL310	0.03
14:51:42	14:52:42	21	Testing fast fill	0.65
14:53:20	14:54:20	22	Testing fast fill	0.87
15:01:32	15:02:32	23	FL100- testing software V.6	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B089**

Date: 05/04/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P		Y
			2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	Y	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann		Y			
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	N	
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov		Y	INC	N	
TWC		Y	CCN / CNC	Y	N
FWVS		N	CVI	Y	N
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red	Y	Y	PSAP	N	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	N
“ JO1D	N		Filters	N	N
Lower Clear	Y	Y	AMS		Y
“ Red	Y	Y			
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N				
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			<u>Others:</u>		
TAFTS		N	NIR TDLAS		N
MARSS		N	2BT O3		N
DEIMOS		N	VACC		N
ARIES		N	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SWS		N	Formaldehyde	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			ADA/CPI		Y
Ozone		Y	NOxy		Y
ECGC	N		PTRMS		Y
NOX		Y			
CO		Y			
ORAC	Y	N			
PAN		Y			
PERCA	Y	N			
WAS		Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B089

Date: 5/04/05

Instruments

1. Video – inboard display goes to standby when in use
2. Core Chemistry SO₂ flow drops to zero at FL150.
3. Mission Scientist Laptop unable to print in colour. Fixed in flight.
4. FWVS serial link cable missing.
5. ADA/CPI WOW cable missing. ADA fibre-optic link damaged.
6. Noxy flows fall below 28kft – data suspect above this altitude
7. Intermittent AMS problems – pump-related?
8. PCASP u/s
9. SID1 computer u/s
10. FASTSSP heater u/s
11. Grimm opc u/s
12. CPC/ams reverse flow problems
13. CCN signal cable either missing or not connected

Aircraft

Satcom phone call?

Foam cladding around ada/cpi rack becoming unstuck.

CCM2 received shock from core chemistry rack – possible static electricity grounding.